

EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG HIGHER SECONDARY TEACHERS

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Abstract:

The present study was conducted to investigate emotional intelligence among higher secondary teachers in relation to certain demographic variables viz. gender, type of management, nature of school, location of school and marital status. Emotional intelligence is denied as one of the important aspects in educating a person to be balanced as a whole. Through emotional intelligence, one will become more successful in life as compared to individuals that gain solely high levels of intellectual intelligence (IQ). Emotional intelligence also provides liberty for individuals to explore self potentials, as well as providing opportunities for individuals to harmonize themselves with their self emotion. Descriptive survey method of research was used for collecting the data using Emotional intelligence by Scale Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Dethe and Upinder Dhar (2001). Sample included 300 randomly selected higher secondary teachers from various schools at vellore City. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to compare the means between the groups. Findings of the study revealed that (1) there is no significant difference between emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers with respect to their gender, type of management, nature of school, location of school and marital status and (3) study revealed there is average level of emotional intelligence among higher secondary school teachers towards the gender, type of management, nature of school, location of school and marital status.

Keys Words: Emotional Intelligence & Higher Secondary Teachers

Introduction:

Emotional Intelligence is the type of Social Intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and other's emotions, to discriminate among them, and to use the information to guide one's thinking and actions.

Perceiving Emotions:

The first step in understanding emotions is to accurately perceive them. In many cases, this might involve understanding nonverbal signals such as body language and facial expressions.

Reasoning with Emotions:

The next step involves using emotions to promote thinking and cognitive activity. Emotions help prioritize what we pay attention and react to; we respond emotionally to things that garner our attention.

Understanding Emotions:

The emotions that we perceive can carry a wide variety of meanings. If someone is expressing angry emotions, the observer must interpret the cause of their anger and what it might mean. For example, if your boss is acting angry, it might mean that he is dissatisfied with your work; or it could be because he got a speeding ticket on his way to work that morning or that he's been fighting with his wife.

Managing Emotions:

The ability to manage emotions effectively is a key part of emotional intelligence. Regulating emotions, responding appropriately and responding to the emotions of others are all important aspect of emotional management. Peter Salovey and John Mayer two psychologists from Yale University coined the phrase emotional intelligence in 1990 in the journal „Imagination, cognition and Personality. However, the concept of emotional intelligence gained popularity through Goleman's (1995) best seller titled Emotional Intelligence. He defined emotional intelligence in 1998 as Emotional Intelligence refers to the capacity of recognizing our own feelings and those of others, for motivating ourselves, and for managing emotions well in our selves our relationships.

Need and Significance of the Study:

All human beings have basic emotional intelligence. This intelligence can be expressed as feelings, for example the need to feel accepted, respected and important while all humans share these needs, each differ in the strength of need, just as some of us need more water, more food, more sleep. One person may need more freedom and independence; another may need more security and social connections. Knowing about one's Emotional Intelligence in terms of an Emotion Quotient has wide educational and social implications for the welfare of the individual and the society. This fact has now been recognized and given practical shape and implication all around the globe. The credit of giving due publicity and acquainting the world-wide population about the importance of books like EI why it can matter more than IQ and working with Emotional Intelligence. A person's Emotional Intelligence helps him much in all spheres of life through its various constituents or components the achievement of the end results in terms of better handling of mutual relationships is quite

essential and significant in his life. It can only be possible through his potential of Emotional Intelligence and its proper development.

Aim of the Study:

The study was aimed on the emotional intelligence among higher secondary teachers.

Sample:

The sample of the study was the higher secondary teachers from different schools in Vellore district, Tamilnadu. The sample was restricted to 300 higher secondary teachers to the investigator for the study. Government, private and aided is considered for the investigation.

Tool:

Emotional Intelligence Scale Standardized by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Detha and Upinder Dhar (2001), Vedant Publications, Lucknow.

Methodology:

The present investigation is meant to study the emotional intelligence and teacher effectiveness among higher secondary teachers from Vellore district. Normative survey method was adopted for the conduct of the present study. The sample consisted of 300 higher secondary teachers randomly selected from vellore district in Tamilnadu. In order to collect data for the study the tool which was constructed and validated by the investigator to assess the Emotional Intelligence Scale by Anukool Kyde, Sunjyat Detha and Upinder Dhar (2001) has been adopted by the investigator for the present study. This tool consisted of 105 items under five alternatives such as strongly agree, agree, uncertain, disagree and strongly disagree which was modified and validated. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.67. This tool is also a five point scale which includes the with scoring 5, 4, 3, 2, 1 respectively for positive items and 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 for negative items.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out the level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers regard to gender.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers regard to type of management.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers regard to nature of school.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers regard to location of school.
- ✓ To study the difference if any, in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers regard to location of marital status.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ The level of emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers is high.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers with regard to gender.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers with regard to type of management.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers with regard to nature of school.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers with regard to location of school.
- ✓ There is no significant difference in emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers with regard to marital status.

Analysis of Data:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of Higher Secondary Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Demographic Variables	Sub - Samples	N	Mean	SD	Level
Gender	Male	157	339.23	81.74	Average
	Female	143	343.54	95.73	
Type of Management	Government	120	336.21	89.39	Average
	Private	131	341.68	90.86	
	Aided	49	352.65	80.56	
Nature of School	Boys	138	341.14	88.31	Average
	Girls	90	341.88	86.68	
	Co education	72	340.81	92.53	
Location of School	Rural	116	338.56	87.26	Average
	Urban	184	343.00	89.57	
Marital Status	Married	189	337.71	88.20	Average
	Unmarried	111	347.37	89.24	

In this study, based on normal curve of higher secondary teachers secured scores in between 252.73 and 429.85 (-1σ to $+1\sigma$) are classified as average emotional intelligence. In the table 1 it was clear that the mean and standard deviation values. The calculated mean values are less than 429.85 and more than 252.73. Therefore, it is found that the higher secondary teachers irrespective of their gender, type of management, nature of school, location of school and marital status have average level of emotional intelligence.

Table 2: 't' test of Male and Female Higher Secondary Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Gender	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	LS
Male	157	339.23	81.74	0.059	NS
Female	143	343.54	95.73		

It is evident from the Table 2 the calculated 't' value is 0.059, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between male and female higher secondary teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Table 3: 'F' test for Sub- samples of Type of Management with Respect To Their Emotional Intelligence

Type of Management	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	9436.133	4718.067	2	0.600	NS
Within Groups	2335909.637	7865.016	297		
Total	2345345.770		299		

It is evident from the Table 3, the calculated 'F' value is 0.600, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of type of management with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers.

Table 4: 'F' test for Sub- samples of Nature of School with Respect To Their Emotional Intelligence

Nature of School	Sum of Squares	Mean Squares	df	'F' Value	LS
Between Groups	51.127	25.563	2	0.003	NS
Within Groups	2345294.643	7896.615	297		
Total	2345345.770		299		

It is evident from the Table 4, the calculated 'F' value is 0.003, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference among sub samples of nature of school with respect to their emotional intelligence of higher secondary teachers.

Table 5: 't' test of Rural and urban Higher Secondary Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Location of School	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	LS
Rural	116	338.56	87.26	0.187	NS
Urban	184	343.00	89.57		

It is evident from the Table 5, the calculated 't' value is 0.187, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between rural and urban higher secondary teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Table 6: 't' test of Married and Unmarried Higher Secondary Teachers towards Emotional Intelligence

Marital Status	N	Mean	SD	't' Value	LS
Married	189	337.71	88.20	1.845	NS
Unmarried	111	347.37	89.24		

It is evident from the Table 6, the calculated 't' value is 1.845, which is not significant at 0.05 level. Hence, the framed null hypothesis is accepted and research hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that there is no significant difference found out between married and unmarried higher secondary teachers with respect to their emotional intelligence.

Major Findings of the Study:

- ✓ It is found that the higher secondary teachers irrespective of their gender, type of management, nature of school, location of school and marital status have average level of emotional intelligence.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their emotional intelligence with regard to their gender.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their emotional intelligence with regard to their type of management.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their emotional intelligence with regard to their nature of school.

- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their emotional intelligence with regard to their location of school.
- ✓ There is a no significant difference between the higher secondary teachers in their emotional intelligence with regard to their marital status.

Educational Implications:

- ✓ Awareness programme should be conducted to the teachers about different dimensions of emotional intelligence.
- ✓ Innovative modern teaching strategies should be incorporated to develop interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligence.
- ✓ Training must be given to teachers regarding language laboratory, digital library, e-library and CAI in order to develop verbal linguistic intelligence among the teachers.
- ✓ Teaching strategies should be developed by using different dimensions of intelligence.
- ✓ Workshops and seminars may be conducted for teachers.
- ✓ In-service training must be given to the teachers to develop their multiple intelligence.
- ✓ Democratic approach in administration will enable teachers to be competent in new areas.

Recommendations for the Present study:

- ✓ Skill based workshops, conferences and seminars must be organized periodically to develop these skills in these areas.
- ✓ Psychological skill based activities to be promoted in teacher education institutions to promote among the teachers.
- ✓ Quality of the programme has to be still more improved to develop the emotional intelligence to teachers.

Delimitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is confined to measure the emotional intelligence only.
- ✓ This study has been restricted only to the higher secondary teachers in Government, government, aided and private,
- ✓ This study is carried out taking 300 teachers as sample.

Conclusion:

One's intelligence is an innate as well as acquired intellectual potential. Every child is born with some intellectual potential which grows and develops with the help of maturity and experiences. Similarly, one is also born with some innate emotional intelligence in terms of one's level of emotional sensitivity, emotional memory, emotional processing and emotional learning ability. This potential (unlike intelligence) is liable to be developed or damaged as a result of one's experiences. The difference here is between the development pattern of innate emotional intelligence and general intelligence as a result of maturity of experiences.

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